

SHORT REPORT

Hearing aids in the treatment of King-Kopetzky Syndrome

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Abstract

King-Kopetzky syndrome (KKS) is a poorly understood neurological disorder which makes it difficult to understand spoken language even though the patient has a normal hearing threshold. There has long been debate about how best to treat patients with King-Kopetzky syndrome. We decided to investigate the effect of hearing aids in this group of patients in more detail.

Main findings

King-Kopetzky syndrome, KKS, (also known as *auditory disability with normal hearing* or *auditory processing disorder*) refers to a neurological hearing disorder characterized by difficulty understanding speech, especially in background noise, despite a normal hearing threshold. King-Kopetzky syndrome has been classified as a central processing and perceptual disorder. Patients with King-Kopetzky syndrome normally complain about hearing impairments in speech comprehension and show abnormal scores on the Social Hearing Handicap Index (SHHI) with normal or only slightly abnormal results on all common hearing

tests.¹ Although the syndrome was described by Samuel J. Kopetzky as early as 1948 and was further investigated by P. F. King in 1954, it is still little known outside the Anglo-Saxon world. Nevertheless, >7% of all patients who consult a doctor about hearing problems are said to suffer from KKS.² The causes of King-Kopetzky syndrome are currently not fully understood. Investigations into familial clustering point to hereditary factors (autosomal dominant) that contribute to the development of King-Kopetzky syndrome. After ruling out other causes (especially other neurological diseases) for the hearing disorder, King-Kopetzky syndrome can be treated by tailored auditory training, stress reduction, loudspeaker amplification systems, treatment of any neurological conditions that may also be present, and of course with hearing aids.^{3,4,5}

We wanted to better understand the role hearing aids play in KKS. To our knowledge, this question is still unresolved. To this end, we sought data from an internationally active hearing aid manufacturer as well as scientifically usable information from people affected by KKS. This was possible after a long run-up and a lot of patience, directly from hearing aid providing entities (clinics, specialized medical shops, etc.) in Brazil, India, the United Arab Emirates and South Africa. Sensitive patient data (103 data sets) was not transmitted, however, we received groundbreaking empirical data regarding our questions which are

1. whether hearing aids have a relevant positive effect on speech understanding in KKS?
2. which models show the best success?
3. whether there are KKS-specific settings on digital hearing aids that need to be considered?

Results

Do hearing aids have a relevant positive effect on speech understanding in PPS? For this subquestion, 89 of the 103 patient records were usable. 12% did not benefit from their hearing aids, 27% reported having slightly less trouble understanding spoken language but considered the effect "not worth hearing," 61% reported a significant improvement in their ability to follow conversations or television with less stress and more clarity.

The models that received the highest ratings were, surprisingly, old-fashioned analog (or digital) amplifiers with no tailored programming for the affected patients. 78 of 103 patients complained until the acousticians deleted finely tuned programs and changed their modern hearing aids into moderately amplifying devices with equal gain values across the entire frequency range. Only 11 patients reported benefiting from tailored programming of their devices, and 14 indicated that both types of devices were helpful. The most striking piece of information was that 25 of 25 patients (100%) wearing hearing aids with a high quality background noise filter reported benefiting "a great deal" from their hearing aids.

Obviously, general amplification of all frequencies with a modern noise filter is the most promising type of hearing aid that really helps KKS patients. Practically, these are devices that are worn behind the ear with closed otoplastics, so that virtually all of the acoustic signals pass through the hearing aid system to the inner ear. This is in stark contrast to the advertising for ever smaller, lighter and more "open" hearing aids. With KKS, the ear canal obviously needs to be completely sealed with an earmold, and the device should have the latest noise-canceling technology. Devices that are worn behind the ear seem clearly superior here.

Conclusion

Hearing aids appear to be of much greater help in King-Kopetzky syndrome than previously thought. However, treatment protocols for KKS patients must be different than for patients with age- or noise-related hearing loss.⁶ Behind-the-ear devices with very good noise reduction, moderate amplification, and earmolds that seal the ear canal well seem to be very important factors in KKS.

Further research is definitely needed.

Conflicts of interest

none

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